

REGENE-PLAST PLASTERS THAT RESTORE DAMAGED SKIN

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Annotation: It has been established that Regena-plast patches, which restore damaged skin, effectively act on inflammation and skin regeneration, do not leave scars on the skin and normalize it. Antibacterial and bactericidal effect, preventing the occurrence of new inflammations, as well as softening and relieving itching. Restores acid-base balance, initiates cell regeneration processes. The patch intensively moisturizes the skin and protects it from dehydration under the influence of external factors (dust).

Keywords: *REGENE-PLAST* patches, damaged skin, biologically active substances, aloe Vera gel, chamomile extract, turmeric, shalfey (*Salvia*).

Introduction: Various skin regenerating and healing agents are of great importance in a number of areas, including medicine, cosmetology and therapy. From treating acute wounds and burns to treating chronic skin diseases and enhancing anti-aging effects, the state of such products requires universal solutions with maximum and rapid effectiveness. Future work in this area may require tools tailored to individual skin types and specific therapeutic needs, as well as the integration of new technologies such as artificial intelligence and biomaterials for greater efficiency and precision. The production of effective restorative and healing products for the skin is a carefully organized process that combines the fields of biology, chemistry and medicine [1-5].

The aim: Being an innovative solution for the restoration and treatment of damaged skin, *REGENE-PLAST* patches are based on increasing the effectiveness of stimulating tissue regeneration and rejuvenation.

The result: Biologically active ingredients: At the core of these plasters are bioactive ingredients with unique properties that support the regeneration and repair of damaged skin. They contain natural extracts, peptides, antioxidants, and vitamins carefully selected for their ability to nourish, protect, and stimulate cellular activity essential for wellness.

The effectiveness of repairing and treating damaged skin on the basis of plasters is that they facilitate the penetration and deeper absorption of skin-

restoring biologically active substances into the skin, as well as protect the damaged skin from mechanical external factors, which ensures optimal therapeutic effects and long-term retention of targeted biologically active substances in tissues. Allows standing.

In the production process of such plasters, the production of skin repairing and healing plasters follows a systematic approach, which begins with the selection and characterization of active ingredients based on their therapeutic properties and suitability.

The initial technical process of the production of plasters includes accurate measurements of the concentration of the necessary substances and the ratio of the ingredients. Quality control throughout the manufacturing process is critical to ensure the safety, efficacy, and durability of wound healing plasters. This requires raw materials, necessary products and hygiene. *In vitro* and *in vivo* studies are being conducted to evaluate the biological activity and effectiveness of the patches, which confirm their ability to promote skin wound healing, reduce inflammation and improve skin integrity. Quality control is necessary to ensure that the final product meets safety, effectiveness and regulatory standards. During the production process, quality control tests, inspections and surveys are carried out.

Several plant extracts included in the patches have been studied for skin regeneration and healing. Added plant extracts widely used in skin care products due to their regenerative and healing properties: aloe vera gel, chamomile extract, turmeric, shalfey (*Salvia*).

Conclusion: Summarizing the main approaches and discussing skin regeneration, particularly recent advances in skin patch technology, including research and currently available commercial topical products, as well as seeking clinical trials using patches to treat wounds resulting from various skin injuries. incorporate and suggest future trends in the biotechnology of clinically applicable skin patches. Although the presence of local manufacturing capacity for damaged skin care influences a country's dependence on imports, countries with a well-developed cosmetics industry and local manufacturing facilities may be less dependent on imported skin care products, including other skin rejuvenation products.

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